

Writing a Blog Script to Promote Pinang Banjar Tourism in Gelumbang, South Sumatra

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ABSTRACT: This study discusses the development of a blog script to promote Pinang Banjar Tourism in Gelumbang, South Sumatra. The writer employed the Research and Development (R&D) method, as described by Sukmadinata (2017), which consists of three stages: Preliminary Study, Model Development, and Final Product Testing. Data were collected through literature studies, field observations, interviews, and documentation. The script was written using the AIDA model (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) and enhanced with visual and structural elements, including a clear title, engaging content, and a call of action. The final product is a blog titled “Pinang Banjar's Rural Natural Charm Presents a Beautiful and Peaceful Atmosphere” published on Blogger. It introduces Pinang Banjar as a tranquil, affordable, and scenic destination, offering activities such as boating and camping. Feedback from language experts, bloggers, and readers showed positive responses regarding both content and design. The blog effectively raises awareness of lesser-known tourism destinations and promotes sustainable tourism practices.

Keywords: *Blog Script, Pinang Banjar, Tourism Promotion, R&D, AIDA*

INTRODUCTION

The South Sumatra Province is rich in natural, cultural, and historical heritage. The province has many tourist attractions, including the famous Musi River with its stunning Ampera Bridge, and ancient sites that preserve traces of the Sriwijaya civilisation. This makes South Sumatra a desirable destination for both domestic and international visitors. Visitors can enjoy the pristine natural beauty of places like the enchanting Ranau Lake and immerse themselves in the cultural richness of the graceful Gending Sriwijaya dance, as well as the luxurious songket fabric.

In addition, South Sumatra also offers fascinating historical attractions, such as the Sultan Mahmud Badaruddin II Museum, which houses a collection of historical artefacts, and Kuto

Besak Fort, a silent witness to the struggle against colonialism. This potential is supported by the region's breathtaking natural beauty, unique cultural traditions, and the warmth of its local community, forming a distinct attraction for travellers seeking authentic experiences (Yoeti, 2013). Therefore, the development of sustainable tourism is a top priority for the local government and all stakeholders, aiming to increase local revenue, create jobs, and preserve the noble values of the local community.

The beauty and promise of South Sumatra, however, extend beyond well-known locations; they are also found in various other areas. For example, Muara Enim Regency and Pinang Banjar in Gelumbang have not yet been thoroughly investigated and effectively marketed. Stunning natural surroundings and a distinctive culture make this a potential tourism destination. Nevertheless, regional tourist marketing plans often fail to recognize and adequately address this local tourism potential. Consequently, the local community's well-being has not been completely enhanced, and the tourist industry's contribution to the regional economy has not been maximized (Pitana & Gayatri, 2005).

The 2024 South Sumatra Province Tourism Village Enhancement Award recognized Pinang Banjar Tourism Village as the winner in the visitor attraction category. With its verdant rice fields and dense woodlands, this tourist destination offers breathtaking natural beauty, making it a distinctive and revitalizing travel destination. In addition, there is a bamboo weaving area in the lake's centre where guests can take in the peace of the breeze surrounding Pinang Banjar. Visitors can also enjoy the view of a lake surrounded by verdant grasslands and witness breathtaking sunsets and sunrises, which create a serene and cozy atmosphere.

Writing engaging blog entries and offering pertinent and helpful information for visitors are two ways to implement an efficient marketing strategy that will expose Pinang Banjar to a broader audience. Aside from having excellent images and videos, blog entries should be written

interestingly. Consequently, the generated blog entries can be a powerful marketing tool and pique travellers' curiosity about Pinang Banjar. Blogging offers several advantages, including problem-solving, insight-gathering, personal development, emotional release, communication, feedback, acknowledgment, and social support, according to Baker and Moore (2011). Promoting Pinang Banjar as Gelumbang's signature product can boost the local economy and raise public interest in travel.

It is intended that more tourists will visit Pinang Banjar due to efficient marketing and excellent blog entries, which will boost the local economy and preserve local culture. The writer will promote Pinang Banjar using a blog in this study. According to the most recent data published by Statista (2024), there are 5.35 billion internet users globally, which accounts for roughly 66.2% of the world's population. Since individuals can readily find and access information about this tourist site, a blog may be an alternate strategy for its promotion. Based on the explanation above, the problem of this article is “How to write a blog script to promote Pinang Banjar Tourism in Gelumbang, South Sumatra?”

METHOD

In this study, the writer employed a Research and Development (R&D) approach to complete the study. Borg and Gal (1983) state that research and development is a process that aims to create and improve products. This process consists of several steps: learning about the results of relevant research related to the product being developed, making the product based on the findings, evaluating the product in its intended environment, and conducting a review to improve its quality. In addition, Sukmadinata (2017) says that research and development (R&D) is a sequence of steps or a process to create a new product or refine an existing one.

The writer decided to use the method developed by Sukmadinata (2017), which consists of three stages: Preliminary Study, Model Development, and Final Product Testing. The

following table presents the stages of R&D developed by Sukmadinata (2017).

Table 1. The Stages of R&D were Developed by Sukmadinata (2017)

Preliminary Study	Model Development	Final Product Testing
Literature Study	Limited Testing	Product Testing
Field Survei	Wider Testing	Dissemination
Model Draft		

In the data collection, the writer employed three methods to collect data: observation, interviews, and documentation. Observation is the act of watching people closely to learn about them. Jamshed (2014) in his journal article explained that it includes not only participants but also field ethnography. It helps to understand how things work by paying close attention and taking notes. The writer collected data by visiting Pinang Banjar ni Gelumbang directly. This village offers visitors a stunning view of the vast lake, set against lush green grass plains that create a calm and cozy atmosphere. The writer observed the situation.

Interviews were activities carried out to obtain information directly by asking questions to experts. In writing this study, the writer used semi-structured interviews to collect data. According to Karatsareas (2022), semi-structured interviews were primarily based on open-ended questions that encouraged participants to develop their thoughts and ideas in depth, express their views on the subject matter from their perspectives, share their experiences, and use their own words. The writer chose to use these interviews because they provided guidelines that allowed for flexible discussions on different research topics and informal questions.

The writer felt more comfortable conducting the interviews and obtained comprehensive information based on the additional questions asked and the objectives in this study. The writer conducted semi-structured interviews with Mr. Dedi Irwansyah, the manager of Pinang Banjar,

and the staff. The interview lasted approximately 20 minutes, covering a total of 8 questions regarding the innovation of Pinang Banjar, its uniqueness, the process of its creation, the products produced, its attractiveness, price range, and the difficulties he faced in introducing Pinang Banjar to the public. Generally, an interview is a conversation between two or more individuals, involving an interviewer and a respondent. It can also be defined as a structured form of oral communication between two or more individuals, whether in person or via remote means.

Sugiyono (2016) stated that documentation is a method used to obtain data and information in various forms, such as books, archives, documents, written figures, and images, in the form of studies or explanations that support research. Documentation is essential as authentic and complementary evidence of observation and interview data. In the documentation method, the writer captured the photo of the view from the

Pinang Banjar and took several pictures that highlighted the unique features of Pinang Banjar. In this step, the writer conducted data analysis using the following steps. After gathering data from observations, interviews, and documentation, the writer classified the data into the script's structure. The introduction, the main body, and the conclusion. After classifying them, the writer started writing the script, beginning with the introduction, main body, and conclusion. In the final step, after the data was written, the writer uploaded the data to the blog using the prepared design.

FINDINGS

The findings in this study are the results of several stages in the research and development process, especially the realization, testing, and revision of the promotional video script. These findings were obtained through direct observation at Green Paradise Resort, literature study,

interviews, and expert validation. Each source contributed to shaping the structure, content, and quality of the final script product in both Indonesian and English versions.

In the realization stage, the writer created the first draft of the promotional video script. This draft was developed using the design blueprint created during the model development phase, which followed a narrative structure of Hook – Introduction – Body – Closing. The content was inspired by field observation and interview data and presented descriptively to create an emotional and informative narrative. The draft was written in both Indonesian and English to ensure accessibility to both local and international audiences.

After the first draft of the video script was completed, it went through a testing process. This stage was important to make sure that the content of the script was suitable, clear, and effective for promotional use. The writer gave the draft to four experts from different fields. Each of them was chosen because of their knowledge and experience. Their roles were to give feedback, corrections, and suggestions for improvement.

The first expert was a script content specialist. She reviewed the structure of the script, the flow of the story, and the emotional appeal of the language. She explained that while the script already followed a good format—introduction, body, and conclusion—some paragraphs needed stronger transitions. She also pointed out that the use of certain words, like “comfort,” “natural,” and “traditional,” was repeated too often, which made the content less dynamic. She advised using more varied vocabulary and suggested improving the storytelling approach to help the audience imagine the experience.

The second expert was a video production expert. He examined whether the script could be turned into an effective video. He focused on whether the words in the script matched the visuals that would appear in the video. He also paid attention to pacing and timing. He recommended some changes in sentence length to make the narration flow better with video

scenes. He suggested adding complete sentences where necessary and using visual-friendly language, like “imagine yourself walking beside the lake” to make the message more vivid.

The third expert was the Indonesian language expert. He checked the Indonesian version of the script. His role was to make sure the grammar, spelling, punctuation, and word choices were correct according to Indonesian language standards (EYD). He gave suggestions to improve fluency, readability, and cultural appropriateness, especially for the Indonesian audience. His feedback helped make the script sound more professional and easier to understand.

The last expert was an English language expert. He gave corrections to the English version of the script. He focused on grammar, sentence structure, clarity, and tone. He explained that the script should use simple, persuasive, and emotionally engaging language, especially for international viewers. He recommended rewording some parts of the script to make them sound more natural and fluent for a global audience.

After receiving feedback from all four experts, the writer made revisions to the script. These revisions included fixing sentence structures, improving transitions between paragraphs, adding stronger emotional elements, and using a wider range of vocabulary. The final result was a more polished and well-developed script that met the goals of being informative, persuasive, and visually engaging.

The final product of this research is an English-language video script designed to promote Green Paradise Resort as a tourism destination in Pagaralam. The script was developed based on real data collected through observation, interviews, and literature review, and then improved based on expert feedback. After a series of revisions, the script was finalized and is now ready to be used in promotional activities.

The final script follows a structured format. It begins with a prologue that introduces the beauty of Pagar Alam. Then, it moves into the main body, where the features of the resort are

described, such as natural attractions, accommodation, cultural activities, and local food. It ends with a conclusion and closing that contains a persuasive call to action. The script also follows the 5A tourism concept: Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Activities, and Awareness. These five elements are clearly shown in the script to highlight what makes the resort special.

The language used in the final version is simple, friendly, and easy to understand. It also uses emotional and descriptive words to help the audience imagine what it feels like to visit Green Paradise Resort. The script is available in two languages—English and Indonesian—so it can be used to promote the resort both to local and international audiences. It is suitable for use in various media platforms, including Instagram, YouTube, and websites.

Overall, the final product meets the objectives of the research. It helps promote a local tourism destination using professional and attractive language. It also supports the idea of sustainable and cultural tourism by showing the natural and traditional values of the resort. Most importantly, the script is flexible and can be adapted into a voice-over for a tourism video, making it a useful tool for real tourism promotion campaigns.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Results of Initial Product Development

Literature Study

The writer read several articles, watched videos on YouTube and TikTok to find information about Pinang Banjar Tourism, and created a blog script. First, the writer read an article entitled “Desa Pinang Banjar, Sajikan Pemandangan Indah Bagi Wisatawan” from www.rri.co.id (2024). Additionally, the writer read the article entitled “Wisata Desa Pinang Banjar, Sajikan Pengalaman Mengesankan Saat Berkunjung,” published on <https://belitong.pikiran-rakyat.com> (2025). The writer obtained a variety of interesting and beneficial information from the articles. After that, the writer read the article “8 Cara buat blog

sendiri, simple dan proven di Blogspot" by Azlina (2023) and watched a YouTube video by Tazkani Adika (2023) entitled "Cara membuat blog gratis di blogger." Therefore, the writer gained valuable knowledge and information for creating a blog script using the provided platform.

Field Survey.

The writer used information gathered through observations, interviews, and documentation in this step. During the writer's visit to Pinang Banjar Tourism, she observed various aspects of the destination in detail, including tourist activities and events. She also observed the visitors who enjoy the stunning natural surroundings while engaging in activities such as camping, renting boats around the lake, or simply relaxing by the water. Using a smartphone, the writer took numerous photos and documented various aspects of the tourist destination, including blog entry materials. The writer also formulated eight interview questions for Mr. Dedi Irwansyah, the manager of Pinang-Banjar Tourism. Figure 1 shows the final product.

Model Draft

After collecting information from the literature study and field survey, the writer created a draft of the script entitled "Pinang Banjar's Rural Natural Charm Presents a Beautiful and Peaceful Atmosphere." The structure of the manuscript paragraphs is divided into three parts: opening, content, and closing. The opening introduces tourist destinations located in Gelumbang. The content section contains information and activities related to Pinang Banjar Tourism. In the closing, recommendations are written for tourists to visit the tour immediately.

Product Testing Results

In this final report, the writer made a blog using the Blogger platform. This is related to the theory presented by Kaapor et al. (2018), which states that blog serves as an online platform where users can explore diverse articles and share their content by registering accounts, engaging through likes, and commenting on them. The type of blog the writer used is a niche blog, which

is a travel blog. This aligns with Shinta's (2021) theory, which states that the niche blog is one of the most popular blog types.

The writing of this script employs the R&D method proposed by Sukmadinata's model, which proceeds through three stages. These stages are (1) Preliminary study, (2) Model Development, and (3) Final Product Testing. Written in a formal language style to ensure that the blog remains informative while also being polite and accessible to a wide range of readers, because Pulizzi (2012) stated that valuable content for the audience is crucial for keeping them engaged. The writer added three important elements to make blogs more interesting, according to Zavesti.com (n.d), namely hook, body, and call to action (CTA). In addition, the writer created a script outline based on Handley (2014), which consists of an introduction, the main body, and a closing that provides a strong invitation or conclusion.

The choice of blog as a medium to promote Pinang Banjar is because blogging fosters communication and social support. This aligns with Baker and Moore's (2011) idea, which posits that blogging enables individuals to express themselves, share personal experiences, and foster a sense of community by engaging with readers through comments and feedback. After the script is written by the writer is tested with experts until it gets the best result. The script was finally implemented into the blog website. The writer added essential elements to the blog homepage, including a title, hook, visual appeal, solid writing, personality, relevant keywords, interlinking, and images. This concept aligns with Hyder's (2015) idea that an effective promotional website should possess eight key features: title, hook, visual appeal, solid writing, personality keywords, interlinking, and images.

Final Product Results

The following figures show the final product of the blog script.

Figure 1. The Final Product

Pinang Banjar's Rural Natural Charm Presents a Beautiful and Peaceful Atmosphere

South Sumatra is known for its rich culture and stunning natural charm. However, not many people know that the area called Gelumbang is a tourist destination that is on the rise and stores unspoiled natural beauty, namely Pinang Banjar. Pinang Banjar Tourism is located in Gelumbang, Muara Enim Regency, South Sumatra. Pinang Banjar Tourism Objects can be reached in about a two-hour drive from Palembang.

The concept of this natural tourism is nuanced by a beautiful countryside. In addition, the friendliness of the local people around the tourist attractions makes it one of the attractions for tourists. The cost of travelling to this place is very pocket-friendly; tourists can pay as little as IDR 10.000 per person, and anyone can travel to this place as much as possible. Pinang Banjar Tourism is also a paradise for photography lovers. These three reasons make this destination perfect for those seeking peace and well-preserved natural beauty.

Pinang Banjar Tourism is mesmerizing visitors with shady trees, clear lake streams, and vast rice fields, making this place suitable for those of you who want to take a moment to unwind from the hustle and bustle of the city. Another highlight of this tourist village is its seasonal variety of attractions. During the rainy season, the natural beauty is seen from the lush trees and some areas submerged in water like a lake. Locals turn the area into a water tourism spot that can be explored by boat. In the dry season, residents utilize the dry land for camping tours and kite festivals.

In this tourist attraction, tourists can go around the lake or the swamps by boat. Tourists can also camp in the area that has been provided. Visitors who wish to stay overnight do not need to worry, as all necessary facilities are provided. Prices start from IDR 5,000 to IDR 65,000. There are several rules for visitors camping here: noise is prohibited, male and female campers must use separate tents unless married, and overnight guests must present their ID to the management when staying at the Pinang Banjar site.

In addition to enjoying camping activities at Pinang Banjar Tourism, visitors can do various other engaging activities that make the vacation experience more memorable. One popular activity is a boat ride across the lake. The fare is only IDR 10,000 per person, including transport to a tourist point in the middle of the lake. Visitors can enjoy the natural scenery from a different perspective while feeling the calmness of the clear lake water. The best time to take pictures is during sunrise or sunset.

Pinang Banjar Tourism is a nature-based tourist destination with a charm unlike any other. Combines the natural beauty of the countryside and the tranquility of an atmosphere that is difficult to find in urban areas. Green rice fields, clear lakes, and complete camping facilities make this place ideal for a vacation with family or friends. So, what are you waiting for? Visit Pinang Banjar and tell me about your experience! I would love to hear it! See you and happy holiday!

Phone:
+62 82278559559

Instagram:
@wisatapinangbanjar

Address:
Desa Pinang Banjar, Kec. Gelumbang, Kab. Muara Enim, Sumatera Selatan, 31171

35 comments:

Labels: Gelumbang Tourism Outdoor Activities Family Holidays Camping Natural Beauty

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The writer concludes that the blog script entitled “Pinang Banjar's Rural Natural Charm Presents a Beautiful and Peaceful Atmosphere” can be used as a medium for promoting one of the tourism objects in Gelumbang, Sumatra Selatan. The script consists of three parts: the introduction, the main body, and the conclusion. The introduction part of the script provides an overview of the iconic Gelumbang. The main body contains information about the natural uniqueness, activities available, and facilities. The conclusion persuades readers to experience the unique beauty and tranquillity of Pinang Banjar Tourism. The writer published the completed script on <https://pinangbanjartourismvillage.blogspot.com/>. The blog was updated on June 10, 2025. After being uploaded, the blog received 481 views and several positive comments, such as "I honestly really want to visit this place" and "Wow, what a wonderful place." This feedback highlights the blogs as a valuable resource for tourists seeking information about travel destinations, especially in facilitating the easy discovery of Pinang Banjar Tourism in Gelumbang, South Sumatra.

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